

EXTERNAL MOBILITY REPORT

**on the activities carried out under the
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*Pop-Lite: Romanian Popular Novels and Their Sub-genres during the Long Nineteenth
Century: digital editing and corpus analysis*
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The objectives of the visit were, in line with the general objectives of the project, to analyse feelings and emotions specific to 19th century literature. In literature, the analysis of feelings can be approached from different perspectives, including studying how authors express emotions, feelings and opinions of characters or analysing readers' reactions to literary works. This is particularly interesting for understanding the emotional impact and emotional connection that books generate in readers.

Nineteenth-century literature was marked by various literary trends and styles, including Romanticism, Realism and Naturalism, which explored different aspects of human experience. Thus, some specific elements related to the analysis of feelings in 19th century literature can be found in:

- Romanticism and the expression of emotions: the Romantic period highlighted strong individual emotions and feelings. Romantic authors focused on exploring passion, love, melancholy and sadness. Romantic poets, such as Lord Byron, Percy Bysshe Shelley and John Keats, wrote poems highlighting the intensity of feeling, especially love and the ephemeral nature of life.

- realism and emotional introspection: during the realist movement, literature focused on presenting the realities of everyday life and the psychological aspects of characters. Writers such as Gustave Flaubert, Fyodor Dostoyevsky and Émile Zola developed complex characters and explored emotions such as jealousy, obsession, regret and anxiety.

- Social and political feelings: 19th century literature also reflected feelings about the social and political changes of the time. Writers such as Charles Dickens and Victor Hugo wrote about social injustice, poverty, inequality and exploitation, highlighting the desire for change and justice.

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- Women's empowerment and expression of their feelings: there is a development of stronger and more independent female characters who have begun to express their emotions and aspirations in more direct ways. Writers such as Jane Austen and Emily Brontë explored women's struggle for emotional and social freedom.

- Symbol construction for emotions: in many works, feelings and emotions are conveyed through symbols and metaphors. These symbols can range from landscapes and natural phenomena to objects and colours and can be used to emphasise particular emotional states and themes.

- Melancholic images of nature: nature played an important role in expressing feelings in 19th century literature. Natural landscapes were often used as settings to reflect characters' emotions and create specific atmospheres.

Looking at 19th century Spanish literature, I noticed that the expression of feelings and emotions was explored in a variety of ways, reflecting the historical and cultural context of that period. There was a varied succession of literary trends in this era, and works covered a diverse range of themes and emotions. Here are some relevant examples from 19th century Spanish literature that illustrate different approaches to expressing feelings and emotions:

1. Gustavo Adolfo Bécquer (1836-1870) - an outstanding poet of the 19th century, known for his romantic poems. In his creations he expressed sadness, melancholy and love, often inspired by nature and his inner moods. His poem *Rima LIII (Love Song)* is an example of a profound expression of love and nostalgia.

2. Benito Pérez Galdós (1843-1920) - The realist novel *Fortunata y Jacinta* (1887) explores the emotional complexities of his characters. The work illustrates the story of two women, Fortunata and Jacinta, and the love triangle in which they find themselves. The work explores the different aspects of love, jealousy and betrayal, providing a comprehensive overview of human emotions.

3. Emilia Pardo Bazán (1851-1921) - Spanish author who wrote about social and psychological issues of the time. Her novel *Los pazos de Ulloa* (1886) explores the passion and emotional conflicts between characters and their impact on the community in which they live.

These examples represent only a small part of the rich Spanish literary tradition of the 19th century. Authors and works from that period addressed a variety of emotions and feelings, reflecting the complexity of the human condition and capturing the essence of their early spirit.

Following my working visit to the Universidad de Malaga, referring to the analysis of feelings in literature, I found that some research or critical works can explore the following aspects:

- Stylistic analysis of language: the study of stylistic techniques, metaphors and the use of language to communicate emotions and feelings in a literary work.

- character analysis and emotional development: examining the development of characters within a novel or story and how they experience and express feelings throughout the narrative.

- Reader reactions: researching readers' reactions and feedback on the emotions and feelings aroused by reading a particular book.
- the impact of literature on readers: studying how books can influence readers' emotional states and how they can generate empathy or emotional connection.

Date,
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Signature,

Mobility beneficiary,
Drd. Oana-Elena Ionescu

Advised,

Prof. Univ. Dr. Rosario Arias Doblas

Signature,

CS I Pop-Lite Project Manager,
Roxana Patras